

Silibinin: a comprehensive review of its pharmacological properties and therapeutic potential

Akanksha Kumari

Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Patel Nagar, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

Mukesh Pandey

Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Patel Nagar, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India

Abstract- Silibinin, is a major bioactive flavonolignan derived from the seeds of *Silybum marianum* L. (milk thistle) plant of the *Asteraceae* family. It has gained considerable attention for its broad-spectrum pharmacological properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, cardio protective, neuroprotective, anti-diabetic, anticancer, immunomodulatory, anti-viral and wound healing effects through modulation of various cellular signaling pathways. Key mechanisms include inhibition of reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation, regulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, induction of apoptosis, and suppression of proliferative signaling via pathways such as NF- κ B, MAPK, and PI3K/Akt. Silibinin has shown promise in inhibiting metastasis, angiogenesis and tumor growth across several types of cancer. Despite its promising therapeutic potential, challenges such as poor bioavailability require innovative delivery systems for enhanced clinical efficacy. However, *Silybum marianum* remains a valuable natural treatment with broad pharmacological effectiveness and the present work reviews the expanding applications of silibinin in the modern medicine.

Key Words- Silibinin, *Silybum marianum*, Milk thistle, Antioxidant, Reactive oxygen species, Antimicrobial, Hepatoprotective, Cardioprotective, Neuroprotective, Cytokines, Apoptosis, Bioavailability

I. INTRODUCTION

Medicines from plants/herbs have been the main stay of the traditional medicinal systems like Ayurveda and Chinese medicine systems from past several centuries [1]. Relatively newer medicinal systems like homoeopathy and allopathy also depend on the extracts or active ingredients obtained or derived from plant/herbal sources [2, 3]. In the lower- or middle-income countries still the traditional medicine serves as the backbone of primary healthcare [4]. The benefits associated with plant based traditional medicines are the easy and local availability of sources, lower cost associated with traditional remedies and lesser instances of adverse reactions [5]. However, traditional medicines have disadvantages associated with them also. The major drawback is the lack of strict regulations to regulate the quality or standardization of traditional medicines at an international level [6]. Many modern countries and the scientific community still consider traditional medicine systems as pseudoscience; thus, they do not appreciate traditional medicines very much or see them as equivalent to modern medicines [7]. However, in the past few decades traditional plant-based medicines again gained some recognition which is very evident from the current market size of traditional medicines. This increase in market size is attributed to several factors, the first one is the national government policies. World Health Organization (WHO) Global Survey on Traditional Medicine 2023, reported that national policies have been formulated and adopted by 100 countries around the world [8]. Another factor is the tilting of world population towards the traditional practices like meditation and Yoga for overall well-being and health management natural products for minor complications and overall, well-being. One other major factor is the necessity to develop newer chemical moieties to enhance treatment strategies against diseases conditions. It also made the researchers look again towards the natural sources of medicines. So, overall, these conditions helped to resurge the interest towards natural source-based medicines.

Nature offers a wide spectrum of sources like plants, herbs, rocks, minerals, and marine sources from which traditional medicines can be obtained or processed. Out of all sources terrestrial plants have been investigated

throughout centuries for their medicinal benefits. Many plants were found to have multiple therapeutic uses and were documented for the same in ancient texts. One such plant species is *Silybum marianum* or milk thistle [9, 10]. *Silybum marianum*, a member of the Asteraceae family, is an annual or biannual plant. These flowers bloom in July and August with distinctive purple-red blooms, where they were originally separated from seeds. Originally from South Africa, Asia Minor, South Russia, and South Europe, the milk thistle has also naturally occurred in Americas, North and South as well as the South Australia. Milk thistle has been used for a very long time in conventional European Medicine [10]. In 1968, silymarin the main ingredient of *Silybum marianum* was extracted from seed and reported to have potential hepatoprotective properties [11].

II. HISTORICAL CONTEXT, TRADITIONAL USE, AND MODERN SCENARIO

Pliny the Elder (first century A.D.), Pedanios Dioscorides (50 A.D.), and Theophrastus of Eresos (fourth century B.C.) were among the first western authors to mention the therapeutic properties of *Silybum marianum* [12]. Milk thistle silymarin extract, which is extracted using an organic solvent and makes up 1.5–3% of the dry weight of the fruit. In the 1970s, the World Health Organization designated it as an official medicine having health-promoting qualities. Fruits from the *milk thistle* plant have been used for almost 2,000 years to treat conditions relating to the liver and biliary system. Milk thistle was part of the herbal medicine arsenal of naturalists and physicians of the Renaissance, who used it as an antidote for liver poisons during the Middle Ages. Preparations of milk thistle fruits were also used by native American Indians, physicians, and herbalists in the 19th century to cure a variety of diseases, particularly liver disorders. The usage of silibinin-dependent, bioactive silymarin extracts has been extensively documented in the past 40 to 50 years to treat liver issues, including cirrhosis, viral hepatitis, nonalcoholic liver disease, drug-induced liver injury, and mushroom poisoning. Compared to patients who are given a placebo, patients with problem of liver treated with silymarin show a quicker improvement in function of the liver. In the same way, giving silymarin to alcoholic liver cirrhosis patients for a number of years produced a much lower death rate [9]. It should be expected that silymarin is a dietary supplements for cirrhosis and hepatitis that is most frequently sold in the USA and Europe [13]. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of the United States has authorized it to be used as a medication for liver treatment in capsules and tablet forms, among other standard formulations. The gastrointestinal system only absorbs 23% to 47% of silibinin following oral treatment, according to pharmacokinetic studies.

According to several studies, silibinin and silymarin are extremely potent antioxidants that can significantly boost cellular antioxidant defense systems. They are roughly ten times more potent than vitamin E and can scavenge both reactive oxygen species (ROS) and Free radicals [14]. Patients with alcoholic liver cirrhosis have a significantly lower death rate while taking silymarin daily for several years, according to a randomized controlled multicenter experiment. After testing silibinin and silymarin in a variety of animal models and dosage forms, no harmful or toxic side effects in lab animals have been documented [15]. Both silibinin and silymarin have been shown *in vivo* studies to be well tolerated and to have no appreciable negative impacts on health. Both compounds have been demonstrated to be non-toxic to experimental animals at various dosages and administration methods with no known harmful health effects [16]. It has been investigated for hepatitis, cirrhosis, poisoning from *Amanita phalloides* mushrooms, cytoprotection from hazardous occupational exposures, and prophylaxis against the adverse effects of chemotherapy in young children with acute lymphoblastic leukemia [11]. In the past ten years, more than 12,000 papers on compounds related to silibinin have been published. These compounds have been employed as chemo preventives, antioxidants, anticancer agents, and most notably, as hepatoprotectives [17]. Strong antiviral, immunomodulatory, antifibrotic properties are displayed by silibinin. Moreover, by preventing cell migration, angiogenesis, proliferation, apoptosis, and growth of tumor, anti-cancer capabilities are demonstrated by silibinin [18]. Anti-inflammation, growth suppression, apoptosis induction, cell cycle regulation, chemo sensitization, multi-drug resistance reversal, inhibition of angiogenesis, and inhibition of invasion and metastasis are only a couple of the many ways that silibinin inhibits certain cancer cells [19]. Silibinin has been investigated in several different cancer treatments and has demonstrated encouraging results against several types of cancer, including Breast, liver, skin, lung, colon, bladder, ovary and prostatic [20]. According to a number of studies, silibinin alters the phospholipid turnover rate, which modifies the physical characteristics of the liver cell membrane [21].

III. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

Silybum marianum contains a diversity of phytoconstituents mostly of phenolic nature. Flavonoids, a subclass of polyphenol phytochemicals which is frequently found in red wine, fruits, vegetables, nuts, seeds, flowers, stems, and spices [22]. Flavonoids have a lengthy evolutionary history of being associated with animal species because they

have been present in nature for millions of years, which probably accounts for their diverse biochemical and pharmacological characteristics [23]. A small subclass of flavonoids known as flavonolignans is made up of a lignan (phenylpropanoid) component and a flavonoid moiety. The flavonolignans were present in four isomeric forms, silybin, isosilybinin, silydianin, and silychristin in the seeds and fruits of *Silybum marianum* [24]. Among these ingredients, silibinin (silybin), is the primary physiologically active ingredient, it is a combination of two diastereomers silibinin A and B that is present in the ratio of approximately 1:1. The silibinin is regarded as an extremely functionalized molecule. One primary, one secondary alcoholic and three phenolic hydroxyl groups are present in silibinin which can be further classified based on their types. Within the structure of silibinin, these five hydroxyl groups are the main targets of the derivatization process to form new moieties. [25]. Silibinin is insoluble in non-polar solvents like petroleum ether and chloroform but exhibit extreme solubilities in polar aprotic solvents like dimethylformamide (DMF), tetrahydrofuran (THF), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and acetone. Silibinin is thought to be safe and doesn't have any significant side effects [26].

Figure 1. Chemical structure of silibinin.

IV. PHARMACOKINETICS

4.1. Absorption and bioavailability-

Zhu *et al.* in their investigation on the oral administration of silymarin found that single oral dosages of silymarin extract at doses of 175 mg, 350 mg, or 525 mg resulted in systemic flavonoid exposure in both dose-proportional and linear manner. They observed that these substances were absorbed rapidly, with T_{max} value (maximum plasma concentration time) for every flavonoid ranging from 1.0-1.5 hours, however, they also get quickly expelled [27]. *In vitro* trials evaluating different pharmacodynamic aspects, shows that flavonolignans plasma concentrations were typically lower after oral administration, because of low absorption, and quick metabolic processing which finally yields low oral bioavailability. Attempts have been made to overcome these restrictions and one such attempt is delivering the silibinin using nanotechnology [28]. In one particular investigation, it is found that the bioavailability of extract of silymarin increased effectively by complexing with soy phosphatidylcholine (PC) [29]. The research showed systemic concentrations of silibinin (i.e., silybin A and silybin B combined) ranging from 5 to 75 μ M were achieved, from silymarin extract formulations (silibinin-PC complex) thus, improving bioavailability [30, 31]. Formation of intermolecular bonds between, the silibinin and PC complex demonstrated stability and selectivity, leading to increased solubilities in organic and lipophilic solvents. It is anticipated that phytosomes have improved capacity to penetrate cell membranes and enter the cells [32]. Numerous investigations conducted *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and on humans have demonstrated that extracts from milk thistle strongly inhibit a single or many CYP450 enzymes [33].

Zhu *et al.* reported in their study as per pharmacokinetic analyses, the greatest plasma concentration out of all flavonolignans in the participants receiving milk thistle extract supplements is of silybin A and silybin B [27]. Pharmacokinetic investigations inside humans and rats demonstrated that silibinin-PC complex's achieves higher bioavailability. When comparison made between silibinin-PC complex, and silibinin-N-methylglucamine complex, silibinin bioavailability in rats was found to be considerably enhanced following oral silibinin-PC complex administration [34]. It was found after oral administration of silibinin-PC combination, silibinin was found in the plasma of rats within few minutes, and it reached at highest level an hour later. After that for six hours, there was no decrease in the plasma levels of silibinin. Following an injection of silibinin-PC complex, silibinin was found in bile

fluid in substantial amounts two hours later, and the liver kept secreting silibinin into the bile for the duration of the trial. The non-complexed form of silibinin, on the other hand, was hardly detectable in the bile during the same timeline. Over the course of 24 hours, the complexed silibinin is 6.5 times more likely to reach into the bile than the non-complexed silibinin (13% versus 2%) [29]. Additionally, it was present in the urine within a few hours and remained eluted for a maximum of three days.

In humans, silibinin if administered via phytosomes improves its absorption and is better able to reach the liver in more concentration. Administering silibinin-PC combination as capsules orally to 20 healthy male volunteers, Li *et al.* were able to demonstrate the same. They observed the highest C_{max} or plasma concentration, at 1.4 hours (T_{max}). Also increased bioavailability was observed [35]. Silibinin-PC complex demonstrated 4.6 times more systemic availability in humans when compared with bioavailability data of noncomplexed silibinin from earlier investigations [36]. In healthy people, a formulation of silibinin-PC complex with silipide (IdB 1016) has demonstrated better systemic availability of silibinin (via oral route) than noncomplexed silymarin only. Furthermore, IdB 1016 was administered for seven days to patients with colorectal cancer with doses of 360mg, 720mg, or 1440 mg. In plasma, the amount of silibinin was reported to be in between 0.3 and 4 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, between 0.3 and 2.5 nmol/g in liver, and in between 20-141nmol/g in the intestinal tissues [37]. A similar formulation when administered in patients with breast cancer demonstrated to provide high blood levels of silybin when taken orally [38]. Moreover, phase I clinical trials showed that silybin-PC complex produced significant maximum plasma concentration into the patients with prostatic carcinoma in research studies [30].

4.2. *Metabolism and elimination-*

Silibinin is typically metabolized via CYP450-2C8 to o-demethylated silibinin (main) as well as (minor) metabolites of mono- and dihydroxy-silibinin [39]. Glucuronide and sulphate conjugates of silibinin were also produced and partially enters the enterohepatic cycle and gets hydrolysed further. However, it happens only when 75–90% of the silibinin dose gets metabolized [40]. Between the two diastereomers of silibinin difference in area under curve in the ratio of 4:1 is observed in bioavailability analysis, which suggests stereoselective absorption, distribution, or metabolism [41]. The half-life of complete silibinin in plasma is roughly six hours. One to five percent of an oral silymarin dosage is eliminated unaltered in the urine. silibinin and silychristin are eliminated in the bile in the form of glucuronides and sulphate metabolites. Silibinin can be recovered from the bile in conjugated form in 20–40% of the dose that was administered to the patient. Feces include the residual amount of silibinin. In cholecystectomized patients with T-tube drainage, silibinin biliary excretion reached a steady state within or less than 2 days after silymarin 420 mg/day was administered split in three doses. Excretion ceased three days after the last treatment. After 24 hours following the oral delivery of 140 mg of silymarin, the maximum silibinin concentrations in the bile in the form of sulphate or glucuronide conjugates was in the range of 10- 50 mg/L. The peak concentration levels remains from 2 to 9 hours [13]. Silibinin is biotransformed in liver cells in both the first and second phases [42].

4.3. *Mechanism of action-*

Silymarin's hepatoprotective activity is imposed in the humans by a variety of distinct metabolic processes. Silibinin acts by inducing polymerase I and rRNA transcription. Silibinin enhances the production of ribosomal RNA (rRNA). This causes the rate of protein synthesis to rise for both structural and functional proteins. The loss or malfunction of both enzymes and transporters that take place in some clinical circumstances can be compensated for by this stimulation. Silymarin prevents α -amanitin, the primary poison from the death cap mushroom (*Amanita phalloides*), from interacting with various parts of the cell, such as nuclear receptors this prevents the polymerase II inhibition as well as the resulting inhibition of the production of proteins) and basolateral transport systems (which prevents uptake of α -amanitin) [43].

V. THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS

5.1. *Antioxidant Activity-*

Flavonoids typically have strong antioxidant properties [44]. Study conducted by Valenzuela et al. reported that silibinin suppresses the peroxidation of lipids generated due to impact of NADPH- Fe^{2+} -ADP and t-butyl hydroperoxide (TBH) and the inhibition is concentration dependent [45]. Studies conducted in rat hepatic microsomes have shown that silibinin dihemisuccinate inhibits peroxidation of lipids caused due to Fe (III)/ascorbate; this inhibition is also concentration-dependent [46]. In terms of antiperoxidative activity, silymarin has been demonstrated to be more active than quercetin and dihydroquercetin, regardless of the experimental paradigm employed to generate peroxidation [47]. According to a recent study, silymarin raises the amount of

oxygen consumed, decreases the production of lipid peroxide, boosts urea synthesis in the medium of perfusion, and decreases lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) loss inside the rats' liver cells exposed to tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TBH). Silymarin can also counteract the rise in Ca^{2+} level that TBH produces by bringing ion concentrations drop to less than 300 nmol/L. Lipid peroxidation suppression mediates silymarin's protective impact, and hepatocyte Ca^{2+} level regulation appears to be a key factor [48]. The antioxidant and scavenging of free radicals qualities of silibinin are primarily responsible for its cytoprotective benefits. Additionally, silibinin can directly interact with the components of cell membranes to stop any anomalies in the lipid fraction content that is in charge of preserving normal fluidity [49].

5.2. Anti-inflammatory Activity-

The anti-inflammatory as well as anti-arthritic characteristics of the active ingredients, present in milk thistle seeds and silymarin stem is primarily derived from their superior antioxidant properties, which scavenge pro-inflammatory free radicals. According to research, silymarin was more efficient in cases of arthritis development as opposed to those cases where arthritis have already occurred i.e. prevention of arthritis from happening. Silibinin and silicinin prevent migration of neutrophils and suppression of Kupffer cells, which impede the process of inflammation. Additionally, they prevent basophils from releasing histamine and the production of inflammatory mediators, such as both leukotrienes and prostaglandins, particularly with blocking the pathway of 5-lipoxygenase. Consequently, the seeds of milk thistle may have both properties anti-asthmatic and anti-allergic [50, 51]. A study that assessed silibinin activity in isolated Kupffer cells found that it had a strong inhibitory effect on the generation of leukotriene B₄ (LTB₄), with an IC₅₀ value of 15 $\mu\text{moles/l}$. However, there was no discernible impact on the formation of tumor alpha necrosis factor (TNF-B) [52]. An important modulator of immunological and inflammatory responses is NF- κ B. Silibinin has been demonstrated to suppress NF- κ B DNA binding activity as well as its okadaic acid-induced dependent gene expression in the HEP G2 hepatoma cell line. However, silymarin did not impact the NF- κ B activation brought on by TNF-B, indicating that silymarin inhibits pathways [53].

5.3. Antifibrotic Activity-

An important part of liver fibrogenesis is played by stellate hepatocytes. They multiply and change into myofibroblasts, which oversee the liver's collagen fiber deposition, in response to fibro genic stimuli (such as prolonged exposure to the carbon tetrachloride or ethanol). The impact of silibinin on stellate cell differentiation into myofibroblasts has been studied recently. According to the results, silibinin, at a 100 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ concentration, downregulates those gene expression from extracellular matrix components essential for fibrosis, decreases the growth of stellate cells extracted from rats fresh liver with roughly 75%, and decreases these cells from becoming myofibroblasts [54]. Additionally, silibinin has been shown to ameliorate rats with in vivo hepatic fibrosis who have had their biliary ducts completely blocked, a technique that results in progressive hepatic fibrosis devoid of inflammation. When compared to controls, silymarin can reduce fibrosis by 30 to 35% when given for six weeks at a dosage of 50 mg/kg every day. A daily dosage of 25 mg/kg is ineffective [55]. When given orally for 55 days at a dosage of 50 mg/kg, colchicine and silymarin had the capacity to completely avoid everything of the changes that carbon tetrachloride caused in rats (lipid peroxidation, Na^+ , K^+ , and Ca^{2+} ATPase), with the exception of the amount of liver collagen, it was just 55% lower than controls; additionally, alkaline phosphatase and ALT remained unchanged. The loss of glycogen was totally prevented in the rat group given silymarin [56].

5.4. Antimicrobial Activity-

Numerous antimicrobial properties, including antibacterial, antifungal, and antiparasitic properties, have been demonstrated by flavones [57]. Among the fungi that cause infections of the mucosa, *Candida* species are too accountable for the blood related infections inside the people [58]. Silymarin slows down *Candida albicans* development, maybe by rupturing the cell membrane, as well as lessens its virulence by breakdown of fully developed biofilms as well as hydrolase excretion [59]. The most dangerous human malaria parasite, *Plasmodium falciparum*, is the cause of the highest rates of morbidity and mortality in the World [60]. Silymarin interacts with heme to cause membrane damage and apoptosis, which lowers the viability of *P. falciparum* with a high selectivity index [61]. Hepatic fibrosis brought on by parasitic granulomatosis and granulomatous response surrounding the parasite eggs are the hallmarks of the parasitic disease schistosomiasis. Hepatic fibrosis and the granulomatous condition are decreased by silibinin periovular reaction without compromising the parasite's ability to oviposit [62]. By invading host cells and forming biofilms, among other strategies, bacterial infections evade the host immune system and the deadly effects of antibiotics. Silibinin prevents bacteria from growing, adhering, and forming biofilms, among other things [63]. Furthermore, silibinin enhances the antibacterial action of aminoglycosides against *Escherichia coli* [63].

Newer antiviral medication are still desperately needed today. One of the participants in the *Flaviviridae* family of positive, single-helix, encapsulated RNA viruses, the hepatitis C virus (HCV) leads to persistent infection in many people and may develop to hepatocellular cancer and liver cirrhosis. Silibinin prevents HCV from replicating by suppressing the activity of genotype 2a NS5B RNA-dependent RNA polymerase. Furthermore, Silibinin lowers to the inflammatory response along with T cell proliferation in addition to blocking HCV entrance and transmission [64]. These findings stimulate additional research into silymarin as a potential new treatment strategy for infectious disorders by indicating that it modulates both the host and microbe responses to produce antimicrobial effects.

5.5. Hepatoprotective Activity-

The hepatic organ is an essential body part for the process of metabolism and elimination of several chemicals, including xenobiotics, lipids, chemotherapeutic drugs, and environmental contaminants [65]. Hepatitis, cirrhosis, fibrosis, and steatosis are the most common characteristics of hepatic disorder. Many hepatic condition, such as nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and alcoholic liver disease, as well as drug toxicity, have been treated with silibinin [66]. Hepatocyte damage and disturbance of lipid metabolism cause excessive fat to accumulate in hepatocytes, a feature shared by both NAFLD and alcoholic liver disease [67]. Hepatocytes convert free fatty acids (FFAs) from adipose tissue and/or chylomicrons (by lipolysis) to triglycerides through β -oxidation or esterification, after which they are either released the very-low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) or retained as lipid droplets. Hepatic steatosis, on the other hand, happens when VLDL-TG secretion declines and FFA absorption, lipogenesis, and lipid storage rise. Silibinin prevents sterol regulatory element binding protein 1, stearoyl CoA desaturase and fatty acid transport protein 5, from being expressed, that prevents lipid induced by FFA buildup in the hepatic cells [68]. Additionally, research has demonstrated that silibinin prevents NAFLD in vivo by reducing liver cholesterol [66].

5.6. Cardioprotective Activity-

The primary cause of death for older persons nowadays is cardiovascular disease, which is typically linked to ischemic damage. *Silybum marianum* has been shown to possess the cardioprotective action in both animal and cellular models of cardiovascular disorders [69]. The primary pathogenic pathways of the cardiac diseases, which includes myocardial infarction (MI), arrhythmia and heart failure, are generally believed to include oxidative stress, cell death and inflammation. By maintaining mitochondrial function through antioxidant actions, silibinin improves myocardial salvage in pig models during the acute stage of MI. Additionally, Silibinin reduces reactive heart fibrosis in the border region by blocking TGF β 1-T β R-Smad2/3 signaling channels, which enhances cardiac repair and heart contractility after MI [70]. Cardiac dysfunction can result from damage to cardiac myocytes caused by the β -adrenergic agonist isoproterenol. Silibinin restores mitochondrial activity and modulates SIRT1 and Bcl-2 to prevent isoproterenol-induced cardiac myocyte damage [71]. Because of their β -agonist arrhythmic effect, inotropes that are positive is frequently utilized for severe cardiac failure treatment but not for long-term heart failure treatment. Remarkably, 2,3-dehydrosilybin shows promising impacts of inotropy without the negative adverse effects of β agonists, hence bolstering its application as potential inotropic drug for heart failure, both acute and long-term treatment [72].

5.7. Neuroprotective Activity-

Research suggests that depression, Alzheimer's disease (AD), as well as other neurological degenerative illnesses are influenced by oxidative stress, neuroinflammation and nitrosative stress [73, 74]. In rats given LPS, silibinin consumption reduced oxidative stress, inflammation, and learning and memory deficits [75]. Furthermore, silibinin shielded PC12 cells treated with sodium nitroprusside from nitrosative stress and the activation of the ROS-brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF)-TrkB pathway, which causes neuronal injury in the LPS-treated hippocampus [75, 76]. Furthermore, brain under the oxidative stress of aged mice was observed to be lessened by *Silybum marianum* oil. The aforementioned findings suggest that *Silybum marianum* might be helpful for both treatment and prevention of neurological conditions [77]. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurological disorder that worsens over time, and it is typified by an accumulation of amyloid beta (A β) peptide, damage to synapses and nerves, and a shortage of acetylcholine. Acetylcholine deficit and A β peptide aggregation in hippocampus cells are two of the main causes of AD [78]. Research has demonstrated that AChE-induced A β polymerisation can be prevented by acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors [79]. Both AChE activity and aggregation of A β or oxidative stress inhibitors are thought to be promising therapeutic medicines that could halt or lessen the course of Alzheimer's disease. Research indicates that the silibinin not only prevents A β peptide from aggregating into the hippocampus cells, furthermore suppresses the ACHE activity and raises acetylcholine levels. Furthermore, isosilybin provided antioxidant protection to hippocampus neuronal cells against A β peptide, potentially by the activating of the NRF2/ARE signaling pathways. [80, 81].

Parkinson's disease (PD) is marked by a progressive loss of dopamine as a result of dopaminergic neurons dying off [82]. 1-Methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine (MPTP) is used to develop a Parkinson's disease (PD) model in mice that exhibits histopathological alterations marked by dopamine depletion and neuronal death. According to a study Silibinin shielded dopaminergic neurons, in an MPTP mouse model of Parkinson's disease substantia nigra, [83]. The symptoms of multiple sclerosis (MS), a possibly debilitating illness, of the central nervous system (brain and spinal cord), include, numbness, weakness, tingling, impaired vision, tightness in the muscles, issues with cognition, and problems with the urine. T-regulatory cells, or Treg are essential into the pathophysiology of multiple sclerosis (MS), where the immunological system, controlled by T-lymphocytes, assaults the protective sheath [84]. The potential of silibinin to prevent MS through Treg induction and activation is suggested by the fact that it not only encourages Treg proliferation but also Treg production of TGF- β and IL-10 [85]. Damage to the brain's physiological function characterizes brain infarction and brain stroke, which are typically brought on by ischemia, which triggers inflammation, oxidative stress and apoptosis [86]. Silibinin has been shown to be prevent the course of neurodegeneration in ischemia models and to postpone hippocampal neuronal cell death. Additionally, by attaching to the extracellular domain of the P2Y₁₂ receptor, Silybin, silydianin, and silychristin prevent blood platelet activation brought on through ADP, potentially reducing the severity of cerebral ischemia and stroke [87, 88].

5.8. Antidiabetic Activity-

Diabetes, a long-term metabolic condition marked by hyperglycemia, frequently results in several problems, such as poor wound healing and memory and learning impairment. A lack of insulin generated by insulin resistance and β -cells in skeletal muscle and hepatic tissue are the main causes of diabetes. *In vivo*, silibinin as well as silybin lower the levels of plasma insulin and blood glucose [89, 90]. One of the main causes of type I diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is the loss of β cells. The β cells of the pancreas secrete human islet amyloid polypeptide (hIAPP) along with insulin, and its components cause β -cell dysfunction through oxidative stress and membrane permeabilization. Silibinin suppresses the harmful oligomerization of misfolded hIAPP, preventing fibrillation and increasing the survival of pancreatic β cells. Furthermore, pancreatic β -cell dysfunction is also brought on by elevated amounts of circulating FFAs. By triggering the ER α pathway, silibinin shields pancreatic β cells from damage to the mitochondria and apoptosis brought on by palmitic acid [91]. An increase in hepatic glucose production (HGP) by the glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis pathways contributes to the disturbance of glucose homeostasis associated with diabetes. Inhibiting gluconeogenesis and glucose-6-phosphatase (G6 Pase) activity, silybin promotes GSK3 β -mediated hepatic glycogen deposition [92]. When excessive glucose levels are present, glucotoxicity occurs, which results in endothelial and malfunction of pancreatic β -cells, including apoptosis reduced GSIS, and intracellular lipid buildup. By triggering the antioxidant response and autophagy pathway, silymarin and silybin prevent hyperglycemia from damaging both human retinal and umbilical vein endothelial cells [93, 94].

5.9. Anticancer Activity-

Numerous research has shown that *Silybum marianum* has anticancer properties against a range of cancer types, including lung cancer, breast cancer, skin cancer, gastric cancer, prostate cancer, leukemia, hepatocarcinoma, multiple myeloma, bladder cancer, colorectal cancer, malignant melanoma, cervical cancer, laryngeal cancer, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, glioma, glioblastoma, and multiple myeloma [95, 96]. For instance, silybin prevents glioblastoma [97], colon cancer, and liver cancer from growing [97-99]. According to studies, silibinin can inhibit the growth of several lines of cancer cells by modifying signaling pathways linked to cell cycle arrest and apoptosis, such as the PI3K, caspase, and signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3) pathways. STAT3 controls the gene expression linked to immunological responses, cell survival, cell cycle, and resistance to standard chemoradiotherapies. In the clinical context, silibinin, is a naturally occurring STAT3 activity inhibitor, stops the development of resistance to cancer treatments mediated by STAT3 [100]. Furthermore, silibinin reduces liver damage and mucositis brought on by radiation therapy *in vivo* and increases the inhibitory impact of methotrexate [101]. Reduced recurrence and case fatality rates are largely dependent on preventing cancer invasion and metastasis. By altering β 1-integrin and the subsequent components D4GDI, Raf-1, and Cdc42, silibinin prevents MDA-MB-231 cells from migrating and adhering [102]. Silibinin meglumine prevents lung cancer without small cells from undergoing the epithelial to mesenchymal transition. Additionally, there is evidence to support the *Silybum marianum*'s use as an adjuvant chemotherapy medication to enhance the anticancer activity and avoid chemotherapy side effects. For instance, silymarin and its constituents shield cardiomyocytes against oxidative damage caused by doxorubicin, which may be caused by the stabilization of the cell membrane as well as the removal of iron and free radicals. Doxorubicin is common anthracycline used in chemotherapy for cancer. The

utilization of *Silybum marianum* (SM), silymarin, and silibinin as possible medications for the cancer treatment is supported by these findings [103].

5.10. Immunomodulatory Activity-

The protective benefits opposed to UVB-induced decrease of contact hypersensitive response were lost when mice given silymarin received an intraperitoneal an endotoxin-free injection neutralizing against-II-12 antibody. Additionally, silymarin medication prevented their wild-type mice—but not the IL-12 mutant animals—from seeing a decrease in the UVB-induced contact hypersensitivity response. Additionally, compared to mice exposed to silymarin plus UVB or UVB alone, IL-12 knockout animals that were either silymarin-treated or not and obtained an intraperitoneal (I.P.) injection of IL-12 reacted more strongly to contact hypersensitivity. These imply that IL-12 mediates the protective effect of silymarin in protecting mice from UVB-induced immunosuppression [104]. The representation of the CD80 as well as CD86 is considerably reduced by silibinin. Dendritic cells (DCs) derived from mouse bone marrow exhibited, class I and II of Histocompatibility Complex Molecules (MHC) which were associated with defects in the DCs' expression of lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced II-12. Endocytosis mediated by mannose receptors allowed DCs treated with silibinin to capture antigens (Ag) with remarkable efficiency. Silibinin has been demonstrated to block translocation of the NF- κ B p65 subunit to the nucleus as well as the Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKS) are activated by LPS [105]. Silibinin's effects on caspases could be a typical cell-mediated immune response, and the DCs treated with silibinin showed a molecular basis for an anti-inflammatory and anticarcinogenic faulty activation of the response and its effects. A separate study suggests that silymarin may help lessen dopaminergic neuron damage and the creation of therapeutic adjuvants that activate microglia and generate inflammatory mediators that need to be immunosuppressed, like immunity to infectious TNF- α and nitric oxide (NO). The levels of LPS-induced nitrite, mRNA, proteins and INOS, were significantly reduced in a manner that is depending on dosage [106]. T-lymphocyte activity is inhibited and inflammatory processes are initiated when silymarin is given parenterally [107].

5.11. Antiviral Activity-

Silibinin slows the inflammatory and cytotoxic chain of events that the virus generates, which may help treat viral hepatitis even if it has little effect on viral replication. Silibinin may be used to treat individuals with chronic hepatitis C by blocking transcription in human hepatoma cells that is dependent on nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF α) expression in anti-CD3 activated human mononuclear cells in peripheral blood [108, 109]. Silymarin has antiviral and anti-inflammatory properties. In reaction to silybin and dehydrosilybin, the human keratinocytes (HaCaT) as well as the human hepatoma cell (HepG2) lines used demonstrated reduced basal and catalytic activity of CY1A1 induced by dioxin. The inhibiting impact of the substances under dehydrosilybin was a far more potent inhibitor than silybin, and the study was more noticeable in HaCaT cells than in HepG2 cells [110]. HepG2 (p53 intact; hepatitis B virus negative) and Hep3B (p53 mutant; hepatitis B virus positive) cells showed a strong growth inhibition response to silibinin. Its cytotoxicity was associated with the production of apoptosis and was somewhat greater in Hep3B cells. In HepG2, it also resulted in G1 arrest, but it caused in Hep3B cells, both G1 and G2-M arrests. Silibinin decreased cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK-2), cyclin D1, cyclin D3, cyclin E, and CDK4 levels in both cell lines while increasing ip1/p27. In cells of Hep3B, silybin as well decreased the amount of the G2-M regulator protein. Additionally, Silibinin dramatically decreased the activity of CDC2 kinase, CDK2, and CDK4 in these HCC cells [111].

5.12. Wound healing activity-

Wounds are physical injuries that cause the skin to open or break, and mending wounds properly is crucial to restoring the skin's functional status and disturbed anatomical continuity [112]. Wound healing and tissue repair are intricate processes that start with inflammation and progress via a number of biochemical and cellular processes, including granulation tissue development, reepithelialization, and extracellular matrix remodeling [113]. Macrophages primarily control the elimination of fibrin and the proliferation of fibroblasts during the inflammatory phase. Only once the inflammation has stopped will the wound begin to heal [114]. Even if the healing process happens spontaneously, an infection can cause significant delays by extending the inflammatory phase, interfering with normal clotting processes, encouraging abnormal leukocyte function, and finally postponing angiogenesis [115]. Antioxidants prevent oxidative damage by combating excess protease and reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are frequently produced by neutrophil buildup in the wound site. Excess ROS and antioxidants may destroy fibroblasts and other cells, protecting against these negative outcomes [116]. Silibinin has the ability to scavenging free radical activity [117]. Inhibition of free-radical producing enzymes (xanthine oxidase, NADPH oxidase). In response to the damage to tissues human body activates nuclear factor kappa beta (NF κ β) and upregulates of

proinflammatory proteins like interleukins (IL1 β & IL6) and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α). This results in inflammation around the ulcers. Silibinin downregulates IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF α and interferon- γ) and enhances levels of anti-inflammatory interleukins (IL-10 and IL-20) which helps in reducing inflammation. Therefore, because of its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities silibinin is found to be very helpful in accelerating wound healing process [118].

VI. CONCLUSION

Traditional medicines have been the backbone of healthcare systems from several past centuries and still serve as a strong foundation of healthcare systems in middle- and low-income countries. Many plants based medicines are known to have multidimensional medicinal benefits. This article reviews the historical background and current medicinal applications of silibinin which have been documented for medicinal use in ancient literature for over 2000 years and is now being extensively researched by the scientists for its therapeutic benefits. Silibinin has shown potential against several therapeutic disease conditions and disorders. It has been tested for antioxidants, anti-inflammatory, antifibrotic, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, antidiabetic, anticancer, antiviral, immunomodulatory, wound healing in both animal models and human subjects. Silibinin have become a center of attraction in medical research for its multidimensional medical utility and is a potent therapeutic agent for treating various ailments.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ROS: Reactive oxygen species
 WHO: World Health Organization
 USA: United States of America
 DMF: Dimethyl formamide
 THF: Tetrahydrofuran
 DMSO: Dimethylsulfoxide
 FDA: Food and drug administration
 AUC: Area under curve
 rRNA: ribosomal ribonucleic acid
 NADPH: Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate
 ADP: Adenosine diphosphate
 LDH: Lactate dehydrogenase
 TBH: tert-butyl hydroperoxide
 TNF α : Tumor necrosis factor alpha
 HCV: Hepatitis C virus
 NAFLD: Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease
 FFAs: Free fatty acids
 VLDL: Very-low-density lipoprotein
 MI: Myocardial infarction
 TGF β : Transforming growth factor-beta
 AD: Alzheimer's disease
 AChE: acetylcholinesterase
 A β : Amyloid beta
 PD: Parkinson's disease
 MS: Multiple sclerosis
 HGP: Hepatic glucose production
 STAT3: Signal transducer and activator of transcription 3
 IP: Intraperitoneal
 HepG2: Human hepatoma cell
 CDK-2: Cyclin-dependent kinase

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